

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF MARKS OBTAINED AT THE B.ED.
EXAMINATION(2013) OF S.M.T.GOVERNMENT
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION

Dr. Naik Tarsing

Assistant Professor

S.M.T. Government College of Education, Kolhapur.

Abstract :

This present paper reports the analytical study undertaken the relationship between internal marks and annual theory examination marks of teacher students. The practical marks is related to teacher educators attendance and punctuality, teacher educators attitude and methodology in teaching, teaching-learning process, teacher students performance and student teacher feedback, student educator and students teacher evaluation. There obtains a very close correlation between a conclusion that might somewhat modify these who are septic about giving weight age to internal assessment as lacking reliability.

Key words :

Assessment, Evaluation, Examination, Teacher students, feedback internal marks, and Theory examination marks, weight age of practical marks.

Introduction:

The training institution is concerned with the development of trainee teacher in all round development of his physical, social and emotional, teaching knowledge, skills, and personality qualities. During the process of the teacher training of the teacher students has to be continually appraised with regard to the level of his intelligence, attainment, aptitude and interest and the method of teaching-learning, various skills to be adopted. The traditional system of examinations which primarily measures the academic achievements. Several research studies are being made to bring to light the drawbacks of this system so that remedial steps can be taken. The weight age given to the internal marks in the final evaluation of a teacher –students achievement in one such step. In examination and measurement the emphasis is upon includes all

the changes that take place in the development of a balanced personality and measure the qualities of teacher students. The researcher to investigate the relationship between the final theory examination and internal marks in various practical's. The scheme of examination in the B. Ed. Degree course is as under

Part I

Paper I :Education in Emerging Indian Society

Section I: Philosophical Foundations of Education

Section II :Sociological Foundations of Education

Paper II :Development of Learner and Teaching Learning Process

Section I:Development of Learner

Section II : Psychology of Learning and Teaching

Paper III :Secondary and Higher Secondary Education

Section I :Secondary and Higher Secondary Education – History and Issues

Section II : School Management

Paper IV : Essential of Education Technology and Information Technology

Section I : Essential of Education Technology

Section II : Information Technology

Paper V : Trends in Education and Electives

Section I : Trends in Education

Section II: Electives (Action Research, Environment, Guidance and counseling. Population Education etc)

Paper VI: Specialization in Methodology

Section I : First Method (English, Marathi,Hindi,Mathematics)

Section II: Second Method(History,Geography,Science,Commerce)

All the papers carry 100 each and each section carry 50 marks .In the six papers all the marks assigned at the annual examination. Practical related to six theory Paper is 60 marks assigned by the teacher educators.

Part II

Practicum Marks

College work		Practice Teaching Examination	
Micro teaching -	30	Two Lessons-	80
Class Room Teaching –	110	Oral Examination-	20
Simulation Teaching -	10	Physical and Health Education-	20
Content Cum methodology -	20	Creativity and Personality	
Models of Teaching -	20	Development Programme-	20
Information Technology Lesson -	10	Educational aids-	20
SUPW-	20	Practical Related to Theory Paper-	60
Internal Examination-	20	Assignment(per Paper2)-	20
Action Research-	50	Internship-	50
Total practical mark 600.			

The teaching profession requiring through knowledge as well as practical skills. Teacher students work with the physical body. The training is totally related to practical work. Practical work develop the teacher students work with the complex of the human mind and personality.

The practical work is based on long established learning theory such as feedback, guidance, demo, reinforcement, were adopted.

Objectives:

- 1.To compare the internal and theory examination marks of teacher students. .
- 2.To study the teacher student attitude towards practical and theory examination.

Research Sample-

For the present study the purposive sampling method was used for the selection of the sample consisted statistical Analysis of Marks Obtained at The B.Ed. Examination(2013) of S.M.T. Government College of Education.

Analysis under different aspects:

The achievement of teacher students in **Paper I**

Marks	No. of Teacher Students	Xm	d	fd
-10	1	5	-5	-5
11..20	1	15.5	-4	-4
21-30	0	25.5	-3	0
31-40	2	35.5	-2	-4
41-50	11	45.5	-1	-11
51-60	43	55.5	0	0
61-70	21	65.5	1	21
71-80	1	75.5	2	2
81-90	0	85.5	3	0
91-100	0	95.5	4	0
	80			-1

55.375

Paper II

Marks	No. of Teacher Students	Xm	d	fd
0-10	1	5	-5	-5
11..20	1	15.5	-4	-4
21-30	0	25.5	-3	0
31-40	1	35.5	-2	-2
41-50	14	45.5	-1	-14
51-60	34	55.5	0	0
61-70	26	65.5	1	26
71-80	3	75.5	2	6
81-90	0	85.5	3	0
91-100	0	95.5	4	0
	80			7

M 56.375

Paper III

Marks	No. of Teacher Students	Xm	d	fd
0-10	1	5	-5	-5
11..20	0	15.5	-4	0
21-30	1	25.5	-3	-3
31-40	1	35.5	-2	-2
41-50	8	45.5	-1	-8
51-60	43	55.5	0	0
61-70	22	65.5	1	22
71-80	3	75.5	2	6
81-90	1	85.5	3	3

91-100	0	95.5	4	0
	80			13

M 57.125

Paper IV

Marks	No. of Teacher Students	Xm	d	fd
0-10	2	5	-5	-10
11..20	0	15.5	-4	0
21-30	0	25.5	-3	0
31-40	2	35.5	-2	-4
41-50	16	45.5	-1	-16
51-60	34	55.5	0	0
61-70	24	65.5	1	24
71-80	2	75.5	2	4
81-90	0	85.5	3	0
91-100	0	95.5	4	0
	80			-2

M 55.75

Paper V

Marks	No. of Teacher Students	Xm	d	fd
0-10	1	5	-5	-5
11..20	0	15.5	-4	0
21-30	0	25.5	-3	0
31-40	2	35.5	-2	-4
41-50	14	45.5	-1	-14
51-60	43	55.5	0	0
61-70	17	65.5	1	17
71-80	3	75.5	2	6
81-90	0	85.5	3	0
91-100	0	95.5	4	0
	80			0

M 55.5

Paper VI

Marks	No. of Teacher Students	Xm	d	fd
0-10	2	5	-6	-12
11..20	1	15.5	-5	-5
21-30	1	25.5	-4	-4
31-40	0	35.5	-3	0
41-50	4	45.5	-2	-8
51-60	31	55.5	-1	-31
61-70	34	65.5	0	0
71-80	7	75.5	1	7
81-90	0	85.5	2	0

91-100	0	95.5	3	0
	80			-53

M 72.13

Practical Marks:

Marks	No. of Teacher Students		
101-200	0	150.5	0
201-300	3	250.5	751.5
301-400	33	350.5	11566.5
401-500	44	450.5	19822
501-600	0	550.5	0
	80		32140

M 401.75

The result of theory examination and practical marks of each teacher-students were then calculated and statistical analysis was done for further analysis were defined.

The mean of paper six is 72.13 because one optional paper teacher-students were studied and practical of action research marks is 50 support to increase the marks of this paper. The mean of all theory papers marks is in between 55.00 to 58.00. The practical experience is basically related to theory papers.

Conclusion –

The teacher-students come into the profession and as existing teachers learn more and develop new ideas. The teacher training is of a highly complex which requires considerable knowledge a wide variety of skills and positive attitudes. The interesting point here is that teacher educators who carry out curriculum planning in a teacher-students group frequently derive from experience of personal relationship and the practical work in groups. The complex nature of present day teacher-training means that the work of a teacher-educator and teacher-students is no longer simply that of an teacher profession.

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